

COMMUNICATION PATTERNS OF PARENTS' AND TEACHERS' INVOLVEMENT IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

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Communication Patterns of Parents' and Teachers' Involvement in the Social Development of Intermediate Pupils

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Abstract

This research was focused on determining the relationship between parental and teachers' involvement in communication patterns in the social development of intermediate pupils in terms of relationship management, communication skills, and emotional management. In addition, this study is also geared towards determining if there's a significant difference in the communication patterns of parents and teachers as perceived by student respondents when grouped into sex. The study used descriptive research and a survey data-gathering strategy. There were 66 pupil-respondents from Concepcion Pinagbakuran Elementary School. The researcher utilized Percentage Distribution, Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson r correlation coefficient to analyze the data results. The findings revealed that if parents balance Consensual, Pluralistic, and Protective Communication Patterns, the social development of the pupils will be appropriately developed. If teachers provide an assertive communication pattern, it will significantly develop the pupils' social aspects. The Parents' Protective Communication Style significantly affects the pupils' Communication Skills and Emotional Management. Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between the Assertive Communication Style employed by teachers and a child's social development. Meanwhile, the findings indicated that unlike teacher involvement, which is significantly different when classified by sex, parental involvement in communication patterns is typically not significantly different when classified by sex. Therefore, to continue providing the students with the positive communication patterns they need, it is recommended that parents and teachers have a positive and harmonious relationship. For the benefit of the students, who are the most significant component of the school, they ought to engage in active communication to foster a positive understanding of their roles.

Keywords: *communication pattern, intermediate pupils, social development, parents, teachers*

Introduction

As a period where developmental transitions happen, adolescence represents a time when children go through significant life changes. It involves key developmental challenges in their social life. Accordingly, when their social milieu expands, they undergo many forms of adjustments to their social roles. Thus, they need the guidance of the More Knowledgeable Others (MKOs), including their parents and teachers, to help them cope with such developmental transition.

Correspondingly, as stated by Salgado et al., (2021), early adolescence is a phase of development that includes certain fundamental processes of parent-child interaction, which can be characterized as the acquisition of autonomy while safeguarding relatedness. This highlights the importance of establishing a good rapport between parents and their children. Their involvement and support to their children in all developmental phases is important as it reflects the moral compass and the direction of their children's social life in the future. As emphasized by the Institute of Medicine and National Research Council (2015), social competence, which is intertwined with other areas of development (e.g., cognitive, physical, emotional, and linguistic), also may include children's ability to get along with and respect others, such as those of a different race or ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, or economic background. Social competence is multifaceted, and it is a significant area of development since it encompasses a wide range of abilities and attitudes. This suggests that one of a child's essential developmental skills that must be mastered at an early age is social development. Nonetheless, they won't achieve such competence without the involvement and support of the more knowledgeable others, especially the parents and teachers.

Further, embodied by the Department of Education, the Philippine Educational System continues to strengthen its efforts in supporting social development as a key developmental aspect of a child's journey to holistic development. It also recognizes the significant relationship between social development and learning. That is why teachers are tasked with more than teaching lessons; they also guide and mold the learning behaviors and attain the developmental tasks the pupils must achieve at their age (Montilla et al., 2023). The teachers serve as the loco parentis of their pupils, which should establish a strong bond with the parents. Their partnership is essential for the continuous development of the pupils. Further, as counselors, teachers must deeply understand the nature of the children and their diversities to assist them in holistic growth and development. Due to the rapid changes in the developmental transition, the children may experience social disturbance, which can affect their behaviors, overall growth, and development.

Therefore, teachers must be equipped with the knowledge, good personal qualities, and professional training regarding their involvement in their pupils' social development. In dealing with young and innocent minds, their influence has a long-lasting effect on the child's educational journey. In addition, they may also help parents by providing proper guidance and involvement to prepare the pupils for life experiences and challenges. Accordingly, this study focuses on examining how the communication pattern of the intermediate pupils is affected by the level of involvement of parents and teachers. As such, intermediate pupils are at the age where

developmental transitions begin which marks the beginning of adolescence. These developmental changes result in the broadening of social roles of the pupils. It implies that there is a need to study the involvement of parents and teachers to properly guide the children towards attaining social development and help them to cope with such adjustments.

As the parents' and teachers' roles are considered significant aspects for the pupils to attain a positive social development, which directs them in facing various social roles. Thus, Concepcion Pinagbakuran Elementary School has been known to promote social development by offering opportunities to properly guide and track the social life of the pupils. The result of the study will serve as a basis for parents, teachers, and schools' collaboration to appropriately guide pupils in their social development as they cope with adolescent developmental milestones. This will help them to be relatable and deal effectively with children at this critical age.

Research Questions

The focus of the study is to determine the influence of parental and teachers' involvement on communication patterns in the social development of intermediate pupils. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the mean perception of the learners-respondents to their parents' involvement on communication pattern in terms of:
 - 1.1. consensual;
 - 1.2. pluralistic;
 - 1.3. protective; and
 - 1.4. laissez faire?
2. What is the mean perception of the learners-respondents to their teachers' involvement on communication pattern in terms of:
 - 2.1. assertive style;
 - 2.2. non-assertive style;
 - 2.3. aggressive style; and
 - 2.4. manipulative style?
3. What is the perceived level of development on social aspect among intermediate pupils in terms of:
 - 3.1. relationship management;
 - 3.2. communication skills; and
 - 3.3. emotional management?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of learner-respondents on the parents' communication pattern and their social development?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of learner-respondents on the teachers' communication style and their social development?
6. Is there a significant difference in the communication patterns of parents and teachers as perceived by student respondents when grouped into sex?

Literature Review

Communication Pattern

Communication is an essential part of human lives. It is the basic foundation of human interactions that produces relationships. Along with this, it is one of the skills that must be developed to children at a young age, especially in adolescents who faces abrupt developmental changes at their stage.

Thakkar and Sheth (2014) define communication as the process by which individuals establish and maintain relationships. One way that people figure things out and communicate their meanings with one another is through communication. The participants define their own identities and their relationships to the external environment and one another by means of this interaction.

In the home setting, communication plays a vital part in people's lives since it modifies and shapes the structure of the family system (Clark, 2015). The verbal and nonverbal information that family members exchange with one another is referred to as family communication. There's a lot more to interactions between families than just words being exchanged. It has to deal with posture, verbal tones, gestures, and facial expressions. Family members converse to share information, broaden their horizons, and deepen their sense of empathy (Thakkar & Sheth, 2014). Members can't communicate with one another, though. Sometimes, people in the same group are unaware that other people even exist. As highlighted in the study by Hidayah et al., (2021), harmonious connections within the family can be achieved by parents and children having effective communication.

In addition, Solomon Marcus proposed a communication pattern on 1987. Several scholars used this pattern as the basis for their research. The four communication styles are aggressive style, manipulative style, non-assertive style, and assertive style.

Aggressive Style

When someone communicates in an aggressive manner, they frequently voice their own thoughts and emotions without considering the feelings of others. This communication style is founded on the aim to dominate and control the other person by intimidating, insulting, and coercing them.

Manipulative Style

The manipulative style is an expression of the person's desire for a supporting position, where they wait for the ideal opportunity to shine and make a statement. People have a propensity to interpret other people's words in order to uncover their true motivations. A person who uses this communication style stays away from conflicts and freely expresses their thoughts, which may be altered by the other individual.

Non-Assertive Style

The avoidance of confrontational situations and the guarded expressing of one's own opinions, feelings, and thoughts are traits of the non-assertive style. Individuals who communicate in this way typically adopt a distanced, passive stance and infrequently show signs of initiative.

Assertive Style

The ability to communicate freely and without hurting others while expressing one's opinions, feelings, and beliefs is known as an assertive style (Rizeanu, 2013). According to Yogarane (2016) stated that assertiveness is a personality attribute that characterizes a person's behavior when they wish to express themselves without using power.

Parental Involvement in Children's Social Development

Children need a strong support system from their parents to be able to attain appropriate developmental tasks for their age. That is why parental involvement plays a crucial role in the attainment of holistic well-being of every child.

As stated by Casey (2022), students whose parents remain involved in school have better attendance and behavior, greater academic achievement, better social skills, and better adaptation to school. Parental involvement also more securely prepares young students to develop a lifelong love of learning, which is critical to lasting success. In addition, involving parents can help improve children's conduct both at home and in school because they can work together to deal with behavior issues and improve their interpersonal skills (El Nokali et al., 2011). This only indicates that the parents' roles are essential in all areas of development that a child has to go through. Furthermore, language proficiency and psychosocial well-being of children were found to be favorably correlated with home-based parental educational involvement (Wong et al., 2018), and these correlations were established by including children in school activities. Parents' support and awareness of their significant role lead to a stronger involvement on their child's academic and developmental journey.

Further, Llego (2020) highlighted that Children are more likely to perform exceptionally in school and develop socially and emotionally when their parents are involved in their education. Parental involvement has become a source of motivation and a solid foundation for pupils' performance and socio-emotional development. Family factors, such as parental education level, family economic status, and family size, influence children's development (Cen & Aytac, 2017). Accordingly, the results of multiple studies have indicated a favorable correlation between parental involvement in education and academic success (Tárraga et al., 2017). Additionally, research has shown that parental involvement improves their educational achievement and self-esteem (Garbacz et al., 2017), as well as school retention and attendance (Ross, 2016). This proves how important parental involvement improves beyond just academic success of the students. That is why, if they provided proper guidance and support to their children, they tend to become successful learners and acquire positive attitudes as they grow up.

According to National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2019), children need care that supports their overall mental health, including a positive sense of self, and that fosters positive emotional health and well-being. They also need care that helps them learn how to deal with stressful situations, control mood swings, face their fears, and accept failures and frustration. Children may manage emotional arousal, cope, and control behavior with the help of parents and other caregivers. They do this function by expressing love and respect, giving out encouraging words, and creating a sense of security. Support from parents reduces the possibility of internalizing behaviors in children, such as those linked to anxiety and depression, which can hinder their capacity to adjust and perform well at home, school, and in the community.

Teachers' Involvement towards Development

The impact of a teacher on the lives of their students is evident. Youth are the nation's future, accountable for carrying out crucial duties across multiple disciplines and assisting society in various capacities. That's why, teachers' roles are significant in preparing the children for what the future has in store for them. Also, they continuously shape and guide them in every developmental journey they face as they grow old.

Chatterjee (2021) claimed that teachers have a significant influence on adolescents' overall growth and development. As MKOs in school, teachers' roles are beyond just teaching academics, but most importantly guiding them to achieve developmental tasks and redirect their moral compass. Parallely, Sinha (2022) affirmed that teachers' roles are to instill important values, ethics, and discipline in students while also guiding them through their academic path. Teachers foster young brains and assist them to accomplish great things in life. Thus, their strong partnership with parents is essential to positively guide and direct their pupils to ensure success.

In line with this, as mentioned by Bhattacharjee (2021), teachers assess their pupils' strengths and weaknesses and steer them to the finest practices. They not only bring out the best in children, but they also teach them important life skills such as communication, compassion, organization, and presentation. Teachers are the ones who inspire pupils to excel in all areas and assist them in achieving their life goals.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used a quantitative correlational research design specifically a descriptive correlation type of research. A correlation, as defined by Cresswell (2012), is a statistical test that determines the propensity or trend for two (or more) variables or two sets of data to fluctuate consistently. The aim of correlational research is to discover the relationship between two or more variables. Thus, a descriptive survey is an approach appropriate whenever the objects of any class vary among themselves and when one is interested in knowing the extent to which different conditions are obtained among these objects.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 6 Intermediate Pupils, of Concepcion Pinagbakuran Elementary School. The Grade 6 level has two, Section A consists of 34 pupils and Section B with 33 pupils. There was no sampling technique used since the total enumeration of the population is considered the respondents of the study. Thus, the respondents of the study will be all the 67 pupils in Grade 6.

Instruments

The researcher used a descriptive survey questionnaire to be able to achieve the objectives of the study.

Part I of the instrument dealt with the Personal Data Sheet (PDS) of the respondents which includes age, gender, number of siblings

Part II focused on the intermediate pupils' perception on the involvement of their teachers and parents on communication patterns in their social development. On parental involvement the following factors were included: Consensual Communication Style; Pluralistic Communication Style; Protective Communication Style; and Laissez Faire Communication style.

Part III consists of communication styles included on teachers' involvement were: Assertive Communication Style; Non-assertive Communication Style; Aggressive Communication Style; and Manipulative Communication style.

Part IV focused on the intermediate pupils' perception of the effect of parents' and teachers' involvement in communication pattern on their social development in terms of: Relationship Management; Communication Skills; and Emotional Management.

Procedure

The researcher created a letter of request for three Master teachers to act as the research instruments' validators, which her research advisor signed. This was done to ensure the validity of the survey- questionnaire. The researcher ensured that the validators were specialists on the field of the present study so that they could assess the questions' applicability and determine whether any corrections or changes are to be made. The researcher also sent a letter of consent to the district supervisor and school head of Concepcion Pinagbakuran, as authorized by her research adviser, asking for permission to conduct research among the intermediate pupils in Concepcion Pinagbakuran Elementary School.

Upon approval, the final copies of the survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Directions were made apparent to elicit truthful responses. The researcher ensured confidentiality and respected the rights of the respondents. The responses were recorded in a data matrix and submitted to the statistics center. Finally, the results were interpreted after receiving the results from the statistics center.

Data Analysis

The completion of this study relied on the questionnaire as the primary source of information needed to achieve the study's aims. The frequency and percentage distribution, mean, and standard deviation were utilized to analyze the descriptive questions of the study.

While Pearson r Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine the relationship of the independent and dependent variables of the study.

Further the researcher utilized an Independent t-Test of difference to know the significant difference between parents' and teachers' communication pattern and their social development; and between parents' and teachers' communication pattern and their social development when the pupils were grouped into sex.

Results and Discussion

Part I: Respondent's Gender Distribution

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents According to Gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	36	53.73%
Female	31	46.27%
Total	67	100%

As shown in the table, most of the respondents are male consisting of 36 out of 67 respondents which represents 53.73% and 31 are female which garners 46.27%. of the respondents.

Part II: Respondent's Perception on Communication Patterns on Parents'/ Guardians' Involvement in the Social Development of Intermediate Pupils

Table 2. *Perception on Parents/Guardians' Involvement in Terms of Consensual Communication Pattern*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The stakeholders . . .			
1. I don't question my parents/r guardians' ideas	2.85	1.21	Agree
2. I often talk about my feelings with my parents or guardian.	3.51	0.72	Strongly Agree
3. Understands what is important to the adolescent like me.	3.43	0.60	Agree
4. My parents/ guardians try to make sure disagreements don't turn into fights.	3.58	0.68	Strongly Agree
5. I am not afraid to ask my parents/ guardians for what I want.	2.87	0.75	Agree
Overall	3.25	0.42	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2 presents the result of the gathered data from Concepcion Pinagbakuran Elementary School respondents. It illustrated that under the Parent's involvement in the social development of the intermediate pupils in the Consensual Communication Pattern, the pupils strongly agreed that their parents/ guardians try to ensure disagreements don't turn into fights, with a mean of 3.58 and SD of 0.68. Further, the pupil-respondents also strongly agreed that they often talk about their feelings with their parents or guardians, which got a mean of 3.51 and SD of 0.72. This result was supported in the article of Kumar (2023), wherein he emphasized that parents avoid and resolve disagreements immediately through open communication with their children. This proves that parents emphasize conflict resolution by providing a strong communication rapport between their children. On the other hand, the table above shows the lowest mean of 2.85 and SD of 1.21, which implies that among the Consensual Communication Patterns that parents might provide, the pupils agreed that they are not afraid to ask their parents/ guardians for what they want. However, despite being the least, it was still agreed upon by most pupils and could be seen positively.

The overall mean of 3.25 with an SD of 0.42 proved that pupils agreed that parents instill a consensual communication pattern among their children. As stated by Gill (2022), while it emphasizes compliance, the consensual communication style also encourages communication. With the result above, it could be seen how parents maintain a balance between conflict resolution and open communication while maintaining their authority figure. Thus, it can be concluded that parents ensure a harmonious relationship with their children.

Table 3. *Perception on Parents/Guardians' Involvement in Terms of Pluralistic Communication Pattern*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The stakeholders . . .			
1. My parents/ guardians sought my opinions when taking family decisions.	3.01	0.79	Agree
2. My parents / guardians welcome my contributions in family decision making.	2.94	0.70	Agree
3. My parents/ guardians encouraged me to express my feelings and complaints.	3.24	0.77	Agree
4. My parents/guardians are close to me, with open minds and hearts to freely discuss our thoughts, feelings, and future plans.	3.36	0.83	Agree
5. When my parents/ guardians become too controlling or strict with me, they quickly adjust their behavior and compromise.	2.93	0.84	Agree
Overall	3.10	0.50	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

The data in Table 3 revealed the parent's involvement in the social development of the intermediate pupils in terms of Pluralistic Communication Pattern. It indicates that most of the pupils agreed that their parents/guardians are close to them, with open minds and hearts to freely discuss their thoughts, feelings, and future plans, with a mean of 3.36 and SD of 0.83. Furthermore, it is followed by a mean of 3.24 and SD of 0.77, wherein the pupils agreed that their parents/ guardians encourage them to express their feelings and complaints. Raina (2024) concluded that pupils from these families acquire self-reliance and independence.

On the other hand, this table also denotes that among the indicators, the pupils least agree with the statement "When my parents/ guardians become too controlling or strict with me, they quickly adjust their behavior and compromise", with the mean of 2.93 and SD of 0.84. Nonetheless they still agree with this statement as reflected by the mean.

The computed overall mean of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 0.50 signify that parents provide a Pluralistic type of communication pattern. Williamson (2023) stated that if such type of communication pattern promote open discussion and the respectful expression of differing opinions among members, all while supporting one another. Thus, family talks are highly valued (Lock, 2023). This signifies that parents provide a supportive environment where they give emphasis on the importance of open communication.

Table 4. Perception on Parents/Guardians' Involvement in Terms of Protective Communication Pattern

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The stakeholders . . .			
1. My parents/ guardians are the boss and they provide rules for my good sake.	3.45	0.68	Agree
2. I share my real situation and experience with my parents/guardians when they ask me to so that they can always guide and protect me.	3.36	0.79	Agree
3. My parents'/ guardians' rules and advices are an order in my academics and whole personality.	3.43	0.72	Agree
4. My parents/ guardians support me in the decisions they know will be good for me.	3.69	0.50	Strongly Agree
5. My parents/guardians sometimes become disappointed with my views if they were different from theirs and it brings me closer to conflict.	2.93	0.88	Agree
Overall	3.37	0.45	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

The pupils' perception on communication patterns on parents/ guardian's involvement in the Social Development of intermediate pupils in terms of Pluralistic communication pattern, was discussed in Table 9. The highest mean of 3.69 and standard deviation of 0.50 shows that the parents/ guardians. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 2.93 and standard deviation of 0.88 illustrates that among the indicators, parents/guardians are least become disappointed with diverse views of the pupils. However, they still agree with this statement.

The overall mean of 3.37 and standard deviation of 0.45 indicate that pupils integrate protective communication patterns among their students. Parents who employ this communication pattern steer clear of confrontation and stress the value of members' agreement (Williamson, 2023). This further signifies that pupils are very much aware that their parents sometimes become too strict with them for their own welfare. As such when parents employ protective communication pattern, they uphold and enforce family rules and obedience (Effiong & Usoroh, 2020). Thus through this communication style, parents can instill the value of compliance and responsibility.

Table 5. Perception on Parents/Guardians' Involvement terms of Laissez- Faire Communication Pattern

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The stakeholders . . .			
I can't express my feelings and resentment to them because I know they don't have time or it doesn't make sense to them.	2.31	1.05	Disagree
Me and my parents/ guardians are not open with each other	1.93	0.97	Disagree
We don't talk often because they are too busy with their work or activities.	2.07	0.94	Disagree
I decide for myself because they don't care about me.	1.66	0.86	Disagree
We are not extremely close to each other because we don't talk or spend much time together.	1.99	0.98	Disagree
Overall	1.99	0.75	Disagree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 5 presents the parent's involvement in the social development of the intermediate pupils in terms of the Pluralistic Communication Pattern. The pupils' perceptions are not scattered with each other, which means that they all disagreed that their parents provide a laissez-faire communication pattern at their home.

Furthermore, most of the pupils disagreed that they can't express their feelings and resentment to their parents because they don't have time or it doesn't make sense to them, with the mean of 2.31 and a standard deviation of 1.05. This signifies that whether their parents are busy or not, they still provide their children with open communication where they can express their feelings and resentments. Meanwhile, the statement that disagreed by the pupils is the statement that expresses that they're the ones who decide for themselves because their parents don't care about them, got the lowest mean of 1.66 with 0.86 standard deviation among the indicators. As the statement who got the least mean, this indicate that the respondents are all disagreed by this statement who is closer to being strongly disagreed.

It is interesting to note that the overall mean of 1.99 with a standard deviation of 0.75 clearly states that parents do not instill a laissez-faire communication pattern among their children. It is supported by the study of Umennuihe et al., (2023) entitled Relationship between Family Communication Patterns and Conflict Management Styles of Adolescents in Udeno Local Government Area, Enugu State, wherein, laissez faire communication pattern got the least mean which implies that parents do not instill such style. This is mainly because, in laissez-faire communication pattern, families don't connect emotionally with one another. As emphasized by Wrench et al., (2023), such communication pattern is a communication style among families that lacks discourse and consistency, causing families to become emotionally distant from one another. Fortunately, pupils do not experience such communication pattern as it will have a

negative impact on their social development.

Part II: Respondent's Perception on Communication Patterns on Teachers' Involvement in the Social Development of Intermediate Pupils

Table 6. Perception on Teachers' Involvement in terms of Assertive Communication Pattern

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I can express my thoughts and feelings to my teacher.	2.93	0.87	Agree
2. Our teacher makes sure that there is no anger or hatred that each of us feels.	3.48	0.58	Agree
3. Our teacher helps us to resolve our misunderstandings with my friends or classmates.	3.66	0.62	Disagree
4. Our teacher is open to the personal and academic problems we share to him/ her.	3.43	0.55	Agree
5. I am not shy to tell my opinions and suggestions to our teachers because he/she is open-minded to this.	3.07	0.62	Agree
6. Our teacher politely and calmly tells us our mistakes.	3.39	0.81	Agree
Overall	3.33	0.36	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

The data in table 6 indicates the respondent's perception on teachers' involvement on social development in terms of the Assertive Communication Pattern. The statement, Our teacher helps us to resolve our misunderstandings with my friends or classmates, got the highest mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 0.66 which is interpreted as strongly agreed. On the other hand, the statement, I can express my thoughts and feelings to my teacher, got the lowest mean of 2.93 and standard deviation of 0.87. Though this has the lowest mean, it is still interpreted as developed.

To conclude it could be seen that the overall mean is 3.33 with a standard deviation of 0.71, which indicates that pupils agreed that they're teachers instill an Assertive type of Communication Pattern. Based on the result of the study by Marpaung and Ramadhana (2024), the most dominant communication pattern that teachers applied among their learners is Assertive Communication Pattern. Since such style is an excellent means to provide pupils with a conducive environment, it is evident that this style is prominent in the teaching and learning process. Additionally, assertive communicators are skilled at making concessions and coming up with solutions that please everyone (Carion, 2022). Therefore, efficient communication is necessary to achieve the nature of learning itself, particularly in the teaching and learning process.

Table 7. Perception on Teachers' Involvement in Terms of Non- Assertive Communication Pattern

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>My teachers are...</i>			
1. Can't look at us directly every time we discuss and talk.	2.25	1.06	Disagree
2. My teacher does not refuse every request we made in class.	2.81	0.77	Agree
3. We were often reprimanded for our behavior and treatment of him/her.	3.10	0.74	Agree
4. We are allowed to decide on anything that has to do with the classroom.	2.40	0.87	Disagree
5. Rarely talk to us in person, unless it's about the subject.	2.49	0.91	Disagree
6. Obey and let us decide what activities to perform in the class.	2.37	0.83	Disagree
Overall	2.57	0.55	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 7 presents the teacher's involvement in the social development of the intermediate pupils in terms of the Non-Assertive Communication Pattern. Furthermore, most of the pupils agreed that they're often reprimanded for their behavior and treatment by their teachers with the mean of 2.31 and a standard deviation of 1.05. Meanwhile, the statement that disagreed by the pupils is the statement that expresses that their teachers obey and let them decide what activities to perform in the class, which got the lowest mean of 2.37 with 0.83 standard deviation among the indicators.

The pupils' perceptions are not scattered with each other, which means that they all agreed that their teachers somehow provide a non-assertive communication pattern at their home, with an overall mean of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.55. However, the pupils still perceived their teachers with a low-level involvement on manipulative communication style as provided by the mean. Further, as Robboy (2023) claimed, non-assertive communication really seems somewhat advantageous because it is the exact opposite of an aggressive communicator. It offers advantages to pupils like the feeling of safety, preventing confrontation, upsetting no one, and making no waves. Thus, teachers can use a manipulative style but they must always adhere the positive and balanced communication pattern to effectively help pupils to attain social development.

The pupils' perception on communication patterns on teachers' involvement in their social development in terms of Aggressive Communication Pattern, was discussed in Table 8. The highest mean of 2.37 and standard deviation of 0.92 shows that teachers speaks loudly and with authority, which is why they obey immediately whenever she speaks or gives orders.

Further, the lowest mean of 1.61 with a standard deviation of 0.90 illustrates that among the indicators, the pupils disagreed in the statement that their teacher doesn't listen to them every time they express their feelings, emotions and opinions about something. The overall mean of 1.89 and standard deviation of 0.64 indicate that pupils disagreed that their teachers provide an aggressive

communication pattern among their students.

Table 8. *Perception on Teachers' Involvement in terms of Aggressive Communication Pattern*

Indicators		Mean	SD	Interpretation
The stakeholders . . .				
1.	My teacher doesn't listen to me every time I express my feelings, emotions and opinions about something.	1.61	0.90	Disagree
2.	My teacher often blames me for trouble even though there is no proof that I started it.	1.67	0.92	Disagree
3.	My teacher speaks loudly and with authority, which is why I obey immediately whenever she speaks or gives orders.	2.37	0.92	Disagree
4.	I cannot ask questions to clarify lesson/s because I am scared to be scolded by my teacher.	1.93	0.88	Disagree
5.	He/She used to scold me or my classmates to the point of embarrassing me.	1.93	0.90	Disagree
6.	Our teacher is scary to look at that's why I don't often look at him or talk to him unless it's necessary.	1.81	0.92	Disagree
Overall		1.89	0.64	Disagree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

In the study by Marpaung and Ramadhana (2024) Communication Styles During Teaching Learning Process in EFL Classroom, it was found out that the least employed communication patterns among the teachers are aggressive communication pattern. The reason for this is that teachers that exhibit an aggressive communication pattern create a hostile environment in the classroom by intimidating, threatening, and making students feel uneasy.

Table 9. *Perception on Teachers' Involvement in terms of Manipulative Communication Pattern*

Indicators		Mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Our teacher always tells us that he/she will give additional points to our grades to those students who will do what he/she requested.	3.09	0.96	Agree
2.	Our teacher gives the easiest tasks to students who usually agree to him/her.	2.69	0.92	Agree
3.	Asking tricky questions in an attempt to catch the wrongdoer among us.	2.42	1.00	Agree
4.	Seemingly gives positive comments that contain a critical undertone.	2.91	0.75	Agree
5.	Use fear to influence or manipulate our learning behaviors.	1.97	1.01	Agree
6.	Our teacher uses silence as a tool to punish us.	2.34	1.15	Agree
Overall		2.57	0.59	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 9 indicates the summary of the pupils' perception on the teachers involvement on their social development in terms of Manipulative Communication Pattern.

The table shows that teachers show a manipulative communication style when they always tell their students that they will give additional points to their grades to those who will do what they requested, with the highest mean of 3.09 standard deviation of 0.96. On the other hand, the pupils disagreed that their teachers use fear to influence or manipulate their learning behaviors, garnering a 1.97 mean and a standard deviation 1.01. This variable got an overall mean of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.59, which only proves that pupils agreed that their teachers somewhat provide a manipulative communication pattern among their pupils. As stated in an article by Humaans (2023) such communication style has a distinct benefit of being able to manage and manipulate circumstances in order to get desired results. Manipulative communicators can tilt conversations and choices in their favor by employing discreet or deceitful strategies. Also, such communication pattern can be useful in certain situations, like soothing down an unpleasant and aggressive behaviors (Carion, 2022). Thus, teachers could be able to use manipulative pattern if the situation requires them to control situations for the benefit of successful learning outcomes.

Part III: Respondent's Perceived Level of Development on Social Aspect

Table 10. *Respondent's Perceived Level of Development on Social Aspect in Terms of Relationship Management*

Indicators		Mean	SD	Interpretation
Because of the communication patterns of my teachers and parents I learned...				
1.	I had a lot of friends	3.55	0.63	Highly Developed
2.	I learned the proper behavior of being a good friend.	3.69	0.63	Highly Developed
3.	I learned to socialize well with others.	3.54	0.74	Highly Developed
4.	I learned to give respect to the situation of others.	3.72	0.57	Highly Developed
5.	My relationship with others became stronger.	3.55	0.61	Highly Developed
6.	I became closer and more open with my friends.	3.43	0.76	Developed
Overall		3.58	0.48	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 10 presents the perceived level of development on social aspect among intermediate pupils in terms of Relationship Management.

Wherein, it illustrates that the statement, I learned to give respect to the situation of other, got the highest mean of 3.72 and a standard deviation of 0.75 which is interpreted as highly developed. On the other hand, the statement, I became closer and more open with my friends, got the lowest mean of 3.43 and standard deviation of 0.76. Though this has the lowest mean, it is still interpreted as developed by the pupils.

To conclude it could be seen that the overall mean is 3.58 with a standard deviation of 0.48, which indicates that there is a perceived level of development on social aspect in terms of relationship management among intermediate pupils because of the employed communication pattern of parents and teachers. As highlighted by Peyton (2021) learning social skills such as managing relationships is a helpful way to figure out how to act and behave in various settings and with a variety of people. That is why, parents' and teachers' role are important in guiding the learners' developmental journeys, especially the values they must acquire in dealing with individual differences. Furthermore, regardless of age, parents' and teachers' attitudes and the assistance they provide to their children within the framework of these attitudes have a favorable impact on their academic performance as well as their social and personal competencies. (Ben-Tov & Romi, 2019). If they have positive personalities, they will also have positive involvement in every developmental stage of a child's journey.

Table 11. Respondent's Perceived Level of Development on Social Aspect in Terms of Communication Skills

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Because of the communication patterns of my teachers and parents I learned...			
1. Pay full attention when others are talking to me.	3.36	0.77	Developed
2. Talk calmly to other people)	3.60	0.62	Highly Developed
3. Give the one I'm talking to a chance to speak if he/ she wants to say something.	3.61	0.51	Highly Developed
4. Not ashamed to express my opinions and questions in a respectful manner to others.	3.22	0.82	Developed
5. I keep looking into the eyes of the person I'm talking to so I can better understand what he/she wants to say.	3.39	0.57	Developed
6. Accept other people's opinion and attitude with respect.	3.64	0.57	Highly Developed
Overall	3.47	0.38	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00-Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49-Developed 1.50-2.49-Less developed, 1.00-1.49-Not developed

Table 11 shows the perceived level of development on social aspect among intermediate pupils in terms of Communication Skills. The statement, accept other people's opinion and attitude with respect, got the highest mean of 3.64 and a standard deviation of 0.57 which is interpreted as highly developed.

Meanwhile, the statement, Not ashamed to express my opinions and questions in a respectful manner to others., got the lowest mean of 3.22 and standard deviation of 0.82. Nonetheless, though this has the lowest mean, it is still interpreted as developed by the pupils.

Thus, it could be seen that the overall mean is 3.47 with a standard deviation of 0.38, which indicates that there is a perceived level of development on the social aspect among intermediate pupils in terms of communication skills because of the employed communication pattern of parents and teachers. This can be proven by the above result, as their development in communication skills was influenced by their parents and teachers. As highlighted by Jouany and Marctic (2023) an individual's ability to communicate allows them to comprehend other people and circumstances more fully. It facilitates problem-solving and creative idea-sharing while overcoming differences and fostering a culture of trust and respect. That's why, it is important for parents and teachers to employ well-balanced communication patterns to be able to enhance the communication skills of the pupils.

Table 12. Respondent's Perceived Level of Development on Social Aspect in Terms of Emotional Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Because of the communication patterns of my teachers and parents I learned...			
1. Have a positive outlook on life.	3.54	0.61	Highly Developed
2. Calm down and vent whenever I get angry.	3.40	0.65	Developed
3. Take away the grudge against others and replace it with forgiveness.	3.55	0.60	Highly Developed
4. Be understanding and patient with the behavior of others.	3.48	0.63	Developed
5. Be happy with what others are achieving.	3.54	0.56	Highly Developed
6. Manage any negative emotions I feel in any situation.	3.06	0.75	Developed
Overall	3.43	0.40	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00-Highly Developed, 2.50-3.49-Developed 1.50-2.49-Less developed, 1.00-1.49-Not developed

Table 12 indicates the summary of the pupils perceived level of development on social aspect among intermediate pupils in terms of Emotional Management. It shows that pupils attained high development in social aspect when their teachers help them in taking away the grudge against others and replace it with forgiveness, with the highest mean of 3.55 standard deviation of 0.96.

Meanwhile, the statement, Manage any negative emotions I feel in any situation, got the lowest mean of 3.06 and a standard deviation of 0.75. However, this still interpreted as developed by the pupils. As a result, the perceived level of development on social aspect in terms of emotional management got an overall mean of 3.43 with a standard deviation of 0.40, which only proves that pupils attain

development on social aspect in terms of emotional management.

Thus, it can be concluded that protective communication influences the attainment of emotional management skills of the pupils. According to Ecole Mondiale World School (2024), students who have a solid emotional foundation are better able to handle challenges. It is what instructs pupils on how to make wiser decisions, create realistic goals, and appropriately approach challenges. This merely serves to highlight the significance of teacher and parental involvement in communication patterns for children's social development.

Table 13. *Summary Table of the Perception on Parents/ Guardians' Involvement on Communication Styles*

<i>Communication Styles</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Consensual	3.25	Agree
2. Pluralistic	3.10	Agree
3. Protective	3.37	Agree
4. Laissez Faire	1.99	Disagree
Overall	2.93	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

The summary table of the perception on parents/ guardians' involvement on communication pattern in terms of: Consensual; Pluralistic; Protective; and Laissez Faire is presented on Table 13. Accordingly, the results indicate that most of the pupils agreed that their parents employ Protective Communication Pattern with the highest mean of 3.37. It is followed by Consensual and Pluralistic Communication Style which got 3.25 and 3.10 respectively. Furthermore, Laissez-Faire Communication Pattern got the lowest mean of 1.99 in which the pupils disagreed that their parents uses such communication style. In general, the perception on parents/ guardians involvement on communication pattern got a mean of 2.93 which is interpreted as agree. Accordingly, Singla (2020) emphasized that healthy communication fosters self-worth and responsibility; negative interaction results in distracted thought patterns and an unruly lifestyle. Accordingly, in relation to the outcome, it demonstrates how students disagreed with poor communication patterns and regarded their parents' communication styles as favorable. Furthermore, Lansford (2020) highlighted that most of the parents' educational influence usually occurs at home. The home is where all the developmental foundations begin and serve as the comfort zone of a child. Accordingly, Desai (2020) claimed that to develop mentally, socially, emotionally, and physically, a child needs a secure and nurturing home environment in the family

As such, the integration of positive communication patterns would produce a healthy home environment that help pupils in attaining appropriate developmental characteristics, particularly their holistic development.

Table 14. *Summary Table of the Perception on Teachers' Involvement on Communication Styles*

<i>Communication Style</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Assertive	3.33	Agree
2. Non- Assertive	2.57	Agree
3. Aggressive	1.89	Disagree
4. Manipulative	2.57	Agree
Overall	2.59	Agree

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 14 shows the summary table of the perception of pupils on teachers' involvement on communication styles in terms of: assertive, non-assertive, aggressive, and manipulative. As per the result, most of the pupils agreed that their teachers employ the Assertive Communication Style with the highest mean of 3.33. Further, some pupils agreed that their teachers utilize non-aggressive and manipulative communication patterns garnering the same mean of 2.57. However, they disagreed that their parents uses Aggressive Communication Style. Overall, the perception on teachers' involvement on communication style got a mean of 2.59 which is interpreted as agree. As embedded in the theory of communication styles by teachers, Stavropoulou and Stamatis (2017) highlighted that teachers can use nearly any communication style, depending on what is required in a given situation or moment. Therefore, to successfully create harmonious relationships between their students, teachers only need to balance each pattern they use.

Table 15. *Summary Table of the Perceived Level of Development on Social Aspect*

<i>Social Development</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Relationship Management	3.58	Highly Developed
2. Communication Skills	3.47	Developed
3. Emotional Management	3.43	Developed
Overall	3.43	Developed

Legend: 3.50- 4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49 – Agree, 1.50-2.49- Disagree, 1.00-1.49 – Strongly Disagree

Table 15 displays the summary table of the perceived level of development on social aspect of intermediate pupils in terms of:

Relationship Management; Communication Skills; and Emotional Management. Based on the result, the pupils achieved high development on social aspect in terms of relationship management when their parents and teachers were involved on instilling a positive and well-balanced communication pattern. On the other hand, the remaining two variables of social aspect, communication skills, and emotional management got a mean of 3.47 and 3.43 respectively, which were developed by the pupils. Hence, the findings indicate that parents' and teachers' involvement on communication patterns is significant in attaining social development of the pupils. As cited by the theory of Bandura, the Social Learning Theory, children learn through observation and imitation. Therefore, parents and teachers must always foster a positive image and a good role model to the pupils, so that they will be able to achieve and practice positive social development.

Table 16. *Test of Significant Relationship between Perception of Learner-Respondents on the Parents' Communication Styles and their Social Development*

<i>Parents communication pattern</i>	<i>Relationship management</i>	<i>Social Development</i>	
		<i>Communication skills</i>	<i>Emotional management</i>
Consensual	0.147	0.133	0.198
Pluralistic	0.034	.261*	0.183
Protective	0.125	.268*	.255*
'laissez faire	-0.108	-0.051	-0.026

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 16 illustrates the significant relationship in perception of learner-respondents on the parents' communication pattern and their social development. As stated in the table above, the laissez-faire communication pattern has a negative correlation on the social development of pupils. This signifies that such communication pattern might negatively impact the social development of pupils. As such, the more parents provide a laissez faire communication pattern, the lesser the change of enhancing the positive social development of pupils. Nevertheless, as the parents did not provide such parenting type, it could be seen that it doesn't affect the development of the pupils. Furthermore, the other communication patterns such as consensual, pluralistic, and protective, have a positive relationship in the social development of pupils. It implies that the more parents instill such communication patterns, the higher the chance of attaining social development such as relationship management, communication skills, and emotional management. It is important to note that communication patterns such as pluralistic and protective, have a positive significant relationship with pupil's social development in terms of communication skills. Whereby, the result of the correlation also implies the significant relationship between protective communication pattern and the social development of the pupils in terms of emotional management.

The physical, social, and emotional settings that surround a child while they learn constitute their learning environment, which also includes their cultural context (Hawthorne, 2022). Every child can thrive in a supportive learning environment. Children's conduct is shaped by their environment, which prepares them for life's challenges and helps them thrive in a cutthroat society. The way young people behave from an early age will always shape their character and influence their choices for the rest of their lives.

Table 17. *Test of Significant Relationship in Perception of Learner-Respondents on The Teachers' Communication Pattern and their Social Development*

<i>Teachers communication pattern</i>	<i>Relationship management</i>	<i>Social Development</i>	
		<i>Communication skills</i>	<i>Emotional management</i>
Assertive	.389**	.414**	.453**
Nonassertive	0.010	0.071	0.110
Aggressive	-0.004	-0.039	0.082
Manipulative	0.207	0.163	0.211

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 17 indicates the significant relationship in perception of learner-respondents on the teachers' communication pattern and their social development. Accordingly, it could be seen that there is a negative relationship between the aggressive communication pattern and the social development of the pupils in terms of relationship management and communication skills. However, according to the result, aggressive communication pattern has a positive relationship with emotional development. This implies that the more teachers employ aggressive communication pattern, the lower the chance of attaining the social development of the pupils in terms of relationship management and communication skills. But, this also means that employing aggressive communication pattern will also enhance the emotional management of the pupils.

Further, other communication patterns like assertive and non-assertive gains a positive relationship on the social development of pupils. However, among these communication patterns, it was clearly illustrated that assertive communication pattern has the most positive significant relationship on social development of the pupils in terms of relationship management with .389**, communication skills .414**, and emotional management with 453** p value. It is significant to note that among these social development, the most developed is emotional development. This also emphasized that if teachers employ assertive communication pattern the higher the chance of attaining the social development of the pupils. Coristine et al., (2022), claimed that a positive relationship between the teacher and the student in the classroom is an endeavor to establish trust and respect for one another. Teachers could make a lasting connection and impact to their students. Da Luz (2015) stated that good relationships between teachers and students can support the development of self-regulation abilities in children, in particular independence and self-determination. Students who learn to assess and control their

behavior will be able to accomplish both their personal and academic goals. In the long run, this will also lessen the need for redirection and poor performance. Thus, having a strong relationship with students not only helps them become more successful in the classroom, but it also makes classroom a safe and welcoming atmosphere.

Table 18. *Significant Difference in the Communication Patterns of Parents and Teachers As Perceived by Student Respondents when Grouped Into Sex*

		Sex	M	SD	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Parents communication styles	Consensual	Male	3.13	0.44	-2.560	65	0.013
		Female	3.39	0.36			
	Pluralistic	Male	3.07	0.62	-0.426	54.085	0.672
		Female	3.12	0.32			
	Protective	Male	3.28	0.57	-1.794	47.729	0.079
		Female	3.47	0.23			
Laissez Faire	Male	2.10	0.79	1.283	65	0.204	
	Female	1.86	0.69				
Teachers' communication styles	Assertive	Male	3.37	0.39	1.083	65	0.283
		Female	3.27	0.33			
	Nonassertive	Male	2.71	0.60	2.334	65	0.023
		Female	2.41	0.44			
	Aggressive	Male	2.03	0.76	2.088	56.523	0.041
		Female	1.72	0.42			
	Manipulative	Male	2.72	0.62	2.268	65	0.027
		Female	2.40	0.52			

Legend: $P < 0.05$ significant; $P > 0.05$ not significant

Table 18 shows the test of significant differences in the Communication Patterns of parents and teachers as perceived by student respondents when grouped into sex. On parents' involvement on communication pattern, it is illustrated that the Consensual Communication Pattern with a p-value of 0.013 which means that it is the only communication style that has a significant difference on male and female students' perception. It is because the alpha level used is 0.05 and 0.013 is less than 0.05. While, on the other hand, the Pluralistic, Protective, and Laissez-Faire Communication Pattern had seen to have no significant effect when the pupils were grouped into sex. These variables got a p-value of more than 0.05 which asserts that accept the null hypothesis, there is no significant difference.

Meanwhile, on teacher's involvement on communication pattern, it states that the only variable that has no significant difference when the pupils were grouped into sex is Assertive Communication Style. This communication pattern got 0.283 which is greater than 0.05 that further implies the absence of significant difference. Further, the other communication patterns such as Non-Assertive, Aggressive, and Manipulative styles have a significant difference when pupils were grouped into sex. These communication patterns got a p-value of less than 0.05, which expresses a significant difference, thus rejecting the null.

Conclusions

Communication patterns instilled by parents and teachers are significant in attaining the social development of the pupils. If they provide their pupils with a conducive and supportive environment, the child's social development aspect will be appropriately developed.

The result of the first hypothesis saying that the respondents' perception of parents' involvement in communication patterns and the social development of intermediate pupils are not significantly correlated, are as follows: The parents' involvement in terms of Consensual, Pluralistic, Protective Communication Patterns have a significant relationship in the social development of the pupils. Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted. Meanwhile, the parents' involvement in the Laissez-faire communication pattern and their social development are not significantly correlated, which results in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Further, the second hypothesis's result states that the respondents' perceptions of teachers' involvement in the communication pattern and social development of intermediate pupils are not significantly correlated, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Moreover, the teachers' Aggressive communication pattern and the social development of pupils in terms of Relationship Management and Communication skills are likewise not significantly correlated. Hence, the null hypothesis in this respect is sustained.

As such, at the third hypothesis, parents' involvement in communication patterns is generally not significantly different when categorized by sex, in contrast to teachers' involvement, which is significantly different when characterized by sex.

Therefore, to attain the appropriate developmental aspect needed by the pupils at their age, parents and teachers should work together to create a positive and inclusive environment that is responsive to the needs of pupils. A child's holistic development has a major impact on the communication patterns of their immediate environment, which includes their parents and teachers.

Based on the findings and conclusions made, the following points are recommended:

Parents and Teachers. To attain the appropriate developmental aspect needed by the pupils at their age, they should work together to create a positive and inclusive environment that is responsive to the needs of pupils.

Teachers. The results of the study may help the teachers for they may know their role in providing positive communication patterns through creating positive and harmonious relationships with their students and the whole school community.

School Heads may consider this study as a basis for program implementation in maintaining an inclusive and conducive learning environment for pupils and school stakeholders.

School. The study may create a significant impact on the quality of the school environment as school heads and teachers may be aware of their role and part in providing a positive and diverse communication pattern that will enhance the social development of the pupils.

Future Researchers. The findings and recommendations of this study may serve as a good source of accurate and useful information for his future study of those interested in studies related to the influence of parental and teachers' involvement on communication patterns in the social development of intermediate pupils.

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